

Understanding ancient moose populations in the Rocky Mountains: the historic and archaeological evidence

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Abstract

Although moose have become an iconic symbol of contemporary Rocky Mountain ecosystems, their growing abundance in Colorado and the southern Rockies has inspired renewed interest in understanding their regional prehistory. Pleistocene and early Holocene mammal communities in North America included both the elk-moose (*Cervalces*) and the newly-dispersed Eurasian moose (*Alces*), which are challenging to differentiate and whose biogeographic history is poorly understood. Even in areas where moose are well-established today, they are often poorly represented in archaeological assemblages, an issue compounded by logistical obstacles to their zooarchaeological and biomolecular identification. Nonetheless, a careful review of historical archives (newspapers, photos), ethnohistoric sources, and archaeological publications demonstrate a clear record for premodern moose presence in Colorado and the southern Rockies. As rising populations influence contemporary conservation and management choices, a careful interdisciplinary approach to reconstructing prehistoric moose biogeography (that includes paleontology, archaeozoology, biomolecular science, and Indigenous perspectives) is a pressing task for informed decision-making across public and private lands.

Introduction

The prehistory of moose (*Alces*) in North America is both poorly understood and politically contentious. During much of the 20th century, moose abundances were low in Colorado, and as early wildlife management activities began, were at least sometimes noted as absent in official census results (Rocky Mountain News 1929). But since official reintroduction to the state (North Park) in 1978 and subsequent releases in other areas of Colorado, moose populations have grown steadily, reaching more than 3,000 animals at the time of this writing (Bergman et al. 2024). As populations have risen, human-moose encounters have also increased (Velez 2025), with some of these interactions turning into moments of conflict, capture, and relocation.

At the same time, natural resource managers are increasingly concerned about the consequences of growing moose populations for ecosystem health, particularly in Rocky Mountain National Park, where recent research has documented changes to the Park's riparian beaver-willow ecosystem (Cooper et al. 2025). Recently, Cooper et al. (2025) found that moose browsing contributed to the decline of tall willow stands, the loss of beaver habitat, and the emergence of a new grassland state dominated by moose and elk. Park staff and others have begun discussing management interventions to reduce herbivore pressure, including expanding exclusionary fencing, reintroducing carnivores, and even culling moose (Cooper et al. 2025). A central assumption of these discussions is that moose are not native to the park, therefore humans are ultimately responsible for any ecological impacts from moose.

Public communications by park and wildlife officials about moose in Colorado regularly invoke scientific authority, as in the National Park Service's statement: "Experts have concluded they [moose] did not have established populations" (National Park Service 2025a). This assertion appears based on a superficial look at historic records in the 1970's (Andrews 2011:416; Armstrong 1972:306), and more recently, an unpublished internal report which found only a few published records of moose bones in the vicinity of the park (Brunswig 2015). Also appearing in support of this idea are unverified anecdotes, like the tale of a Shoshone man in southern Wyoming in the early 20th century who "didn't know what [a moose] was, because they hadn't occurred there before" (Miller 2024). Such informal archaeological or ethnohistoric inferences do not appear to have been carefully assessed against the full record of the region, either recently or in the past.

Management of modern moose populations will be more effective and biologically sound when grounded in empirical evidence. Here, we assess paleontological, archaeozoological, historical, and ethnohistoric evidence related to moose presence in Colorado. The data demonstrate that moose populations were established in the southern Rockies before their official 20th century reintroduction. Historic records clearly show the presence of male, female, and juvenile moose across northern and central Colorado. Looking to the deeper past, ethnohistoric and archaeozoological evidence indicate prehistoric moose in Colorado in both the early and late Holocene.

The fossil and archaeological record for moose in North America

Moose (*Alces alces*) evolved in Eurasia during the Pleistocene from their parent genus *Cervalces*, also known as the stag-moose or elk-moose (Lister 1993). As a result of their shared evolutionary ancestry, moose and *Cervalces* have remarkably similar postcranial skeletons (Breda 2005). During the Last Glacial Period *Cervalces scotti*, was the largest cervid south of the Laurentide and Cordilleran ice sheets, where it inhabited spruce forests and tundra-edge environments. Its distribution extended from the northeast and midwestern United States through much of Canada and Alaska (Churcher and Pinosof 1987). Deglaciation of the ice sheets began around 19,000 years ago, but a viable terrestrial corridor connecting Beringia to midcontinental North America likely emerged after ~13,500 years ago (Heintzman et al. 2016). In the postglacial era *Cervalces* ultimately disappeared, whereas *Alces alces*, the only surviving giant deer species, expanded southward.

The scientific record, however, provides quite poor resolution as to precisely when *Alces* reached lower latitudes in North America. A recent genomic study listed six specimens of ancient *Alces* from lower latitude contexts, three of which were apparently sampled for genomic analysis (Consolidated Concrete, Alberta; North Liberty, Indiana; and Big Bone Lick, Kentucky; see Meiri et al. 2020). Of these, two actually appear to represent *Cervalces* based on our inspection of antler morphology (Consolidated Concrete MM575) and published cranial characters (North Liberty; Gazin 1938). Another specimen (Big Bone Lick) was later inspected by Adrian Lister at the British Museum of Natural History, who confirmed it to be *Bison*. Three additional published records of southerly *Alces* with late Pleistocene or early Holocene radiocarbon dates are also noted by Meiri and colleagues (2020). Of these, at least one is also *Cervalces* based on published cranial characters (Lang Farm, Illinois; Schubert et al. 2004). Two other early Holocene specimens, from SE Alaska and Alberta, could not be located for morphological reassessment at the time of writing. Interestingly, although DNA extraction did not succeed for other specimens, mitochondrial DNA analysis of the Consolidated Concrete specimen (MM575) grouped this animal with other North American specimens identified as *Alces* (Meiri et al. 2020), despite its *Cervalces*-like antler morphology. Given such ambiguity over early Holocene biogeography of these two taxa, although “moose” have also been reported from early Holocene faunal assemblages in locations like Colorado and Wyoming (Wheat 1979; Anderson 1968), it is difficult to infer what specific animal (e.g. *Alces*, *Cervalces*) might be represented by early southern occurrences.

Moose specimens are rare in later Holocene archaeological sites across North America, even in places where their ancient presence would not be considered controversial. For example, a census of the Alaskan and Canadian Yukon zooarchaeological record found that, among dozens of sites that have collectively yielded tens of thousands of analyzed specimens, only nine produced published moose identifications, and these often represented less than a tenth of one percent of the Number of Identified Specimens (NISP; Saleeby 2002; Yesner 1989). In fact, most North American archaeological assemblages with meaningful quantities of identified moose date only to the most recent centuries, especially during the Little Ice Age (ca. 14th-19th centuries; e.g. Yesner 1989; Martin 1979; Colburn 1987; Skibo et al. 2004; Kay 1997). The reasons for this scarcity of moose in older assemblages are not clear, but they likely include ecological factors (low population density and changing geographic distributions in prehistory), cultural factors (hunting pressure, low hunting encounter rates, taboos, etc.), and methodological challenges (poor preservation of older materials, misidentification or failure to identify isolated occurrences). For these reasons, the assertion that moose never occurred because they are not reported within the small handful of analyzed faunal assemblages within the park boundaries (e.g., National Park Service 2025a) should be dismissed.

Careful zooarchaeological comparisons that would identify or exclude moose have rarely been attempted in most lower latitude archaeological contexts. Full skeletal references of moose are rare in zooarchaeological collections in the United States, meaning that scientists often lack the reference material to help identify moose remains. Although some morphologically unique elements such as antlers and crania are obvious when they occur, other elements can be difficult to differentiate from other large ungulates such as elk (*Cervus elaphus*) or even bison (*Bison bison*). Some popular

biomolecular tools for taxonomic ID, like ZooMS, also cannot currently differentiate moose from close relatives (Trolle Jensen et al. 2020).

Amidst these barriers, published archaeofaunal reports from across the southern Rockies raise the intriguing possibility of a Holocene prehistory for moose (*Alces* and/or *Cervalces*). Our review of the literature uncovered reports of moose at the Jurgens site, near Greeley, CO (ca. 9,000 years ago). At Barger Gulch, a Folsom campsite in Middle Park, Colorado, a specimen was identified as either moose or elk by biomolecular analysis (Wetherbee 2022), and at the Ute-associated Sue site in North Park dating to ca. 1070-1340 CE, researchers identified three specimens as possible moose (Brunswig 2015). Perhaps the most surprising moose identification comes from the site of Lowrey Ruin near Mesa Verde National Park, where moose metapodials were identified by Martin et al. (1936; 1938) in an assemblage likely dating to the Pueblo III period (ca. 1150-1350 CE).

None of these identifications were accompanied by thorough descriptions of the morphological criteria used, or with clear photos. They should, therefore, be treated with caution and verified through zooarchaeological reassessment and supporting techniques like radiocarbon dating, DNA, LC-MS/MS, and other methods before they are used to support wildlife management decisions. Nonetheless, the potential presence of moose in the southern Rockies across many millennia challenges the prevailing assumption that they were absent prior to the late 20th century, underscoring the need for renewed zooarchaeological and molecular investigation.

The ethnohistoric record

Ethnohistories, oral traditions, and other Indigenous sources suggest that moose have a prehistoric and established presence in most of the Native cultures with ancestral connections to the southern Rockies. Summer moose hunts are mentioned in mid-19th century oral accounts from the Wind River Range in southern Wyoming (Smith 1985), contradicting the assertion that Shoshone people had not encountered moose until the 20th century (Miller 2024). An ethnographic visit among Arapaho people in 1890 chronicled a song referencing moose (Mooney 1896), and a 1909 ethnography with Ute people in Whiterocks, Utah (along the border of western Colorado) documented a story about two brothers who hunt and eat a moose (Mason 1910). This and other Ute sources convey serious taboos against moose consumption (Mason 1910) or even interaction (Andrews 2011:55) that are likely to have seriously impacted the animal's archaeological frequency, at least in more recent assemblages. Ethnohistory even encodes moose in Euroamerican contexts - a study of folklore in Middle Park, Colorado in the 1930's referenced a Native story of moose transformation (Ives 1941). Moose appear in many older Colorado placenames, including those near Rocky Mountain National Park - early travel records from the 19th century refer to one of the open valleys along the road into Estes Park as "Moose Park," and dub an associated topographical feature to be "Moose Hill" or "Moose Park Hill" (Longmont Ledger 1884; Sprague 1922). Topographical features mentioned in these accounts appear to describe what is known today as "Moose Mountain," north of Pinewood Springs adjoining Muggins Gulch on the road to Estes Park. Though none of these observations on their own amount to irrefutable proof that moose are native to Colorado, they demonstrate both early Euroamerican and clear pre-European familiarity with moose among

Indigenous people of the southern Rockies, along with cultural reasons for their scarcity in archaeological assemblages.

Historic observations of moose in Colorado

Anecdotal historic observations of moose in Colorado are sometimes acknowledged during contemporary wildlife discussions, but are usually quickly dismissed. Perhaps most famously, in the 1860s one of the first European settlers of the Rocky Mountain Park region, Milton Estes, shot and killed a moose in what is today Estes Park. He speculated that this animal must be “the first moose that ever wandered so far south” (Estes 1939). Today, Estes’ account is sometimes referenced as though it is the only historical instance of moose in the southern Rockies, paired with the unsubstantiated caveat that moose were “not established” or that “the state never sustained a breeding population” (e.g., National Park Service 2025; Miller 2024).

To assess the state of moose in Colorado before their reintroduction, we searched the Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection database (<https://www.coloradohistoricnewspapers.org/>), whose records begin in 1859, for references to “moose,” excluding keywords related to politics, placenames, and sports. For each mentioned sighting, we excluded references that appeared to refer to the same animal or event from different publications (based on time of sighting, demographic of moose sighted, and geographic location). We combined this approach with a literature review in academic databases for publications of ancient faunal records for moose in Colorado, and a search of online historic photo archives, municipal databases and libraries across the Front Range, and biological collections from Colorado in natural history museums with known date and location of collection.

Newspaper and photograph data from public archives across Colorado demonstrate that moose were frequently present across the southern Rockies long before their 1970s reintroduction, contradicting the idea that such sightings were due to isolated or rare dispersal events. Despite Milton Estes’ off-the-cuff speculation that his moose was the first in the region around Estes Park, other accounts mention moose sightings and even successful hunts near both Sweetwater Lake and Estes Park in 1860; three years prior to Estes’ hunt (Estes Park Trail 1943). An 1873 summary of the “wild animals of Middle Park” listed moose among the animals that a trapper had “either killed or seen in the Park or on the mountains that surround it.” (Colorado Miner 1873). A host of similar records appear consistently through the late 19th century across the region, sometimes referencing multiple animals or even whole groups (Figure 1; Table 1). In total, our review identified more than 30 published occurrences of moose in newspapers between 1860 and 1970, most concentrated across northern and central Colorado (Figure 1, Table 1). Evaluating the time series of media sightings, we observe that published moose observations were consistent, though sporadic, from ca. 1860 through the early 1940’s, when records of moose became even more common (Figure 2). Together, these findings demonstrate the persistent presence of moose across the Colorado Rockies for well over a century prior to their 1978 reintroduction.

Importantly, reports of female moose co-occurring with males and juveniles demonstrate that moose were reproducing locally in the Rockies before their reintroduction. Despite assertions that

this region “never sustained a breeding population,” cows appear nearly as often as bulls in historical newspaper reports and photographs, and juveniles accompanied by mothers were reported on multiple occasions across the study period (Table 1, Figure 2, 3). Moose are often seasonally migratory and young moose, particularly males, are capable of long dispersals of up to hundreds of kilometers (Hoffman et al. 2006), but adult female moose have stable home ranges and continue to return to yearling ranges year over year (Cederlund et al. 1987). Calf moose tend to remain in close proximity to the mother’s home range (Cederlund et al. 1987). Observations like these are thus highly likely to have been made within a stable home range of a breeding population.

Figure 1. Moose sightings in Colorado from historical (1860-1970) sources, museum collections, and published archaeological identifications. Observations labeled by year and indicated by color gradient (black to white indicates older to younger, respectively).

Although historical encounters with moose in Colorado often drew enough attention to warrant commemoration in newspapers, the analyzed records give strong reason to suspect that many, if not most late 19th and early 20th century moose encounters went undocumented. Many of the earliest accounts of moose came from a small handful of preserved diaries or oral accounts shared with curious researchers, and did not appear to regularly reach headlines until the mid-20th century (Table 1). But other media show that moose were obviously present during these early decades. For example, a photo of a 1912 hunt of a cow and calf moose (identified in photo archives at the Pike’s Peak Library District) was not mentioned in any of our surveyed media records (Figure 3). This photo was apparently taken near the Almgren railroad lumber camp near Fairplay, where moose are also incorporated into local placenames (e.g. “Moose Creek”). Our analysis also shows that

historically, moose were often misidentified upon encounter. Several newspaper accounts describe how a hunter seeking an elk only recognized the animal as a moose after killing it (Steamboat Pilot 1941; Wray Gazette 1944; Craig Empire Courier 1950). In 1944 a moose was confiscated from a dismayed elk hunter near Willow Creek near Grand Lake along Rocky Mountain National Park’s western boundary, and accessioned to the Denver Museum of Nature and Science (Arctos record: DMNS:Mamm:6745; Wray Gazette 1944). If moose sightings often failed to reach newspapers and other records, and were often only identified after a fatal hunt, it is a near-certainty that the record assembled here captures only a fraction of their true presence on the landscape in Colorado during the 19th and 20th centuries.

What do these sightings, and their notable increase during the 1940s and 1950s, tell us about actual moose abundance? A rise in newspaper mentions could indicate new dispersal events from adjacent states, but it could just as easily relate to rising visibility or numbers of animals that had long persisted in remote basins, increased human populations, higher rates of recreation, hunting or backcountry travel, changes in media interests and publication rates, or some combination of the above. Given moose are capable of long-range dispersal and well adapted to rugged terrain, all of these explanations remain plausible.

Historical Moose Sightings in Colorado, 1860–1970

Figure 2. Occurrence timeline of newspaper, dated photos, and diary accounts referencing moose sightings in Colorado. Symbols indicate demographic categories of observed animals (see key in figure).

Amidst today’s rising moose populations, competing narratives have emerged about their place in Colorado and southern Rockies ecosystems, each with different implications for how moose should be managed against the backdrop of rapidly changing ecosystems. A closer look at the writings of earlier scientists shows that the thinking around moose’s status has shifted dramatically over the last century. In the 1940s, some biologists working in the Colorado Rockies considered moose a native taxon that had been “extirpated except for stragglers” (Hunter and Yeager 1949). In the 1970s, biologists and park staff working on moose translocation represented their efforts publicly as a “reintroduction” (Golden Transcript 1973; Duvall and Schoonveld 1988), although were ultimately persuaded to abandon this narrative (Andrews 2011). In the decades since, park staff and some biologists have come to see moose instead as “recently introduced” (Cooper et al., 2025). Our analysis suggests that valid knowledge held by earlier scientists, who were more familiar with the 19th

and early 20th century presence of moose in Colorado, has since faded or been displaced, repositioning moose from returning natives to ecological outsiders.

Figure 3. Adult female and juvenile moose shot by Eric Almgren, a “tie chopper” (railroad lumber worker) acquiring food for the Almgren tie camp near Fairplay Colorado, dated to ca. 1912. Courtesy of Regional History & Genealogy, Pikes Peak Library District, 001-7513.

Efforts by the National Park Service to protect Park landscapes from significant changes to contemporary faunas reflect ideology and priorities dating back to the agency’s foundation (Lyman 1998). However, by the time Colorado’s parks were founded in the early 20th century, the southern Rockies had already undergone over two centuries of rapid and dramatic ecological reorganization, including the Columbian Exchange and demographic collapse of Native nations, which left environments deeply altered and destabilized (Jones and Fisher 2023). In many national parks and other federally managed landscapes, well-described and well-dated faunal assemblages necessary for understanding ancient wildlife trends are rare. And while fossil and subfossil records can provide important context for managing historical wildlife populations (e.g., Miller et al. 2021, 2023; Terry 2010), not all records are created equal. Zooarchaeological sources and historic records are often low-resolution, capable of identifying a species’ presence, but less definitive in documenting their absence. Prehistoric data suffer from complex sampling issues, and not all records are able to address all questions.

Misinterpretation of gaps in the historical and archaeological records as “evidence of absence” has been used to justify biologically costly management decisions on federal lands. As a parallel example,

mountain goats were released into Olympic National Park, located on Washington's Olympic peninsula, in the 1930's. Despite historical records pointing to an earlier presence for the animals in the region, and a poor reckoning with the area's archaeological evidence (Lyman 1998), the park deemed the animals invasive. The outcome of this designation was a decades-long effort to eradicate mountain goats, using extraordinary means including helicopter-based removal and culling/slaughter (National Park Service 2025b). The spectre of similar measures looms large for moose in Rocky Mountain National Park.

Moose face significant challenges across much of North America as they reckon with climate warming, disease, habitat fragmentation, vehicle collisions, and other 21st century mortality risks (Timmerman and Rodgers 2017). Their local success in the southern Rockies is just one part of a complex and shifting pattern across the continent, as animal communities respond to rapid environmental change. For wildlife managers grappling with how to tackle rising moose populations in Rocky Mountain National Park and other areas of Colorado, our results indicate that treating moose as invasive, and pursuing eradication or removal on that basis, would be scientifically unsupported. Instead, park and wildlife officials should adopt a sustainable management approach that acknowledges moose presence prior to the establishment of federal management regimes. Scientifically justified efforts to reduce moose impacts might include carnivore introduction or selective hunting access, particularly for Tribes with longstanding ties to the region and that likely played a key role in maintaining pre-contact moose populations at lower densities (Kay 1997).

Conclusion

Premodern records reveal that moose were a part of Colorado's ancient biota, and are not invasive. Our review of the paleontological, archaeological, historic, and ethnohistoric records provides conclusive evidence that moose were present and established in the southern Rockies during the 19th and 20th centuries before their 1978 reintroduction, and likely long before. References to male, female, and juvenile animals in recorded observations clearly indicate viable reproducing populations, rather than merely isolated instances of individual dispersals. Moose are scarce and difficult to identify in archaeological and paleontological assemblages, but the zooarchaeological literature also includes multiple published moose records within Colorado, dating back millennia. Recognition of moose as a part of the native ecology of the region should prompt those making federal and state wildlife management decisions to consider consultation and engagement with paleobiologists, archaeologists and Native leadership. These consultations will lead to a holistic understanding of the moose's distribution and importance in Colorado ecosystems, a requisite for developing holistic management strategies.

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Table 1. Moose sightings in Colorado based on historic sources (newspapers, photos), museum records, and published archaeological identifications. All occurrences are also visualized in Figures 1 and 2.

Source	Location	Year	Sex	Source
Archaeology	Barger Gulch	~ 10500 BCE	Unknown (IDs: Moose/elk)	Wetherbee 2022
Archaeology	Jurgens/Kersey	~7250 BCE	Unknown	Wheat 1979
Archaeology	Sue (5JA421), North Park	~1070-1340 CE	Unknown (IDs: Possible moose, Moose/elk, Moose/bison)	Brunswick 2015
Archaeology	Mesa Verde	~ 1250 CE	Unknown	Martin 1936, 1938
Journal (secondhand account)	Estes Park	1860	Unknown (x2)	Estes Park Trail, 1943
Newspaper	Sweetwater Lake	1860	Unknown	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Estes Park	1863	Male	Estes 1939
Journal	South Park	1870	Unknown	Bailey 1944
Newspaper (narrative account)	Middle Park	1873 or before	Unknown	Colorado Miner 1873
Newspaper	Steamboat Springs	1878	Unknown (multiple)	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Journal	Sweetwater Lake	1887	Male (skeletal remains)	Bailey 1944
Newspaper (secondhand account)	Steamboat Springs	1880's	Unknown	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Glenwood Springs	1895	Unknown (multiple)	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Williams Fork	1895	Unknown (multiple)	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Elk River	1897	Male	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Photo archive	Fairplay	1912	Female, Juvenile	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection

Newspaper	Rio Grande National Forest/San Luis Valley	1925	Male	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Oral account	Routt County	1933	Unknown	Bailey 1944
Newspaper	Steamboat Springs	1941	Male	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Williams Fork/Hot Sulphur Springs	1943	Male, Female, Juvenile	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Troublesome Creek, Hot Sulphur Springs	1944	Male	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Museum specimen	Willow Creek/Grand Lake	1944	Male	Denver Museum of Nature and Science/ARCTOS
Newspaper	Grizzly Creek/North Park	1949	Male	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	North Fork of North Platte	1949	Unknown	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Snake River	1950	Female	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Hahn's Peak	1950	Male	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Whiskey Park	1950	Female, Juvenile	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Willow Lakes, Dillon	1952	Male	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Maybell	1952	Female	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Craig	1952	Female	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Minturn/Holy Cross	1952	Unknown	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Williams Fork/Hot Sulphur Springs	1953	Male	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Snake River	1960	Unknown (x3)	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection

Newspaper	Elk River/Steamboat Springs	1960	Female	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Meeker	1965	Male	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Piceance Creek	1965	Male	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection
Newspaper	Lay	1968	Male	Colorado Historic Newspapers Collection